

Rare earth elements marking soil development at the Geoglyphs of Acre (Brazil)

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Abstract

Earthen structures were built by ancient populations in very different contexts and chronologies. In the western Brazilian Amazon region, in the state of Acre, several earthen structures called “Geoglyphs” have been found. The questions involving the use, extension and geographic distribution of these earthen structures are still completely open. The first excavation carried out by our team (2022) in the Reserva Extrativista Chico Mendes (RESEX), showed that the archaeological materials is limited to some few ceramic shreds, lithic materials and palaeo-biological remains. The aim of this study is to test for the first time the potential of rare earth elements to provide proxies for identifying layer development and distinguish human related activities in soil sample sections from two excavated Geoglyphs located in RESEX. Forty-five samples of sediment were collected from the Antonio y Felipe and Pedro y Nelida Geoglyphs. Rare earth elements concentrations together with major elements and cross-referenced with the archaeological record show that the geochemical information can potentially become a complementary tool to better understand the human contribution to the stratigraphic formation in these contexts.

Keywords:

Rare earth elements, Geoglyphs, chemical elements, earthen structures, soils

1. Introduction

Earthen structures were built by ancient populations in very different contexts and chronologies. Also, the Amazon area is characterised by the presence of earthworks initially named “Geoglyphs” by the researchers due to the apparent resemblance to the Peruvian Geoglyphs of Nazca, to attract the attention of scientists on the importance of this discovery. Earthen structures have been identified in a wide geographical area, showing the ability of ancient populations to manipulate their surroundings and significantly modify the natural environment and create a long-term landscape. The Geoglyphs are especially found in the Western and Southwestern Amazon (Southeast and Southwest of the current Brazilian Amazonas, Acre and Rondônia) and in the north-western area of Bolivia in current territory of Beni, which covers approximately 600 kilometres in length (Fig. 1).

This work is focused on Acre State region, where more than four hundred earthen structure sites have been identified in the deforested areas (Erickson et al. 2008; Schaan et al. 2012) and our case studies are in Reserva Extrativista Chico Mendes (RESEX) area, a Brazilian national reserve where several earthen structures (Geoglyphs) have been found, some of which are dated between 2500 BC and 1400 AD.

Earthen structures were built by European Neolithic and Copper Age populations in very different contexts and chronologies from the 6th millennium BC to the 2nd millennium BC. The hypotheses developed are multiple: some support the idea that the shortage of stone in the environment could have given rise to the construction of these ditches; others suggest that the construction was of social significance, in memory of certain people or events of collective importance; or perhaps a manifestation of respect and/or gratitude to their divinities or ancestors. Other hypotheses are related to astronomical concepts, physical and/or symbolic delimitation, or function such as settlements, ceremonial centres, megalithic graves, and social power management; or simply for drainage, channels of irrigation or animal farming; or some that suggest a defensive purpose (Bernabeu et al. 2006; Erickson et al. 2008; Shaan et al. 2012).

The aim of this study is to test for the first time the potential of rare earth elements (REE) to provide proxies for identifying layer development and distinguish human related activities in sediment sample sections from two recently excavated Geoglyphs located in RESEX.

Chemical processes are known to modify REE ratios in sediments. REE analyses have been recently employed to help in the identification of anthropogenic deposits on archaeological sites by comparing

the REE values from known anthropogenic stratigraphic units to layers with no evidence of human influence (Gallello et al. 2017; 2019a; 2019b; 2021; 2022; Selvaraj et al. 2024).

However, in the investigated Geoglyphs the archaeological record is poorly represented and the natural chemical processes are predominant, therefore, to better understand the strata formation in the studied environment, REE parameters were calculated and cross-referenced with the obtained major element and trace element data. REE concentrations obtained from the analysed sediments samples were normalised, and ratios such as La_n/Yb_n , La_n/Sm_n and Sm_n/Yb_n used to determine relative REE enrichment or depletion. Ce and Eu anomalies were calculated to evaluate differences between measured concentrations of Ce or Eu and the concentration expected of neighbouring REE. Correlation between REE and other elements were also tested to identify significant drivers (i.e., elements) that are affecting the REE chemistry in the different materials. The interpretation of these results could potentially provide important information about the consistency of the mechanisms influencing REE chemistry in the studied sections.

Furthermore, in this first test the data obtained from the excavated profiles may allow us to understand if REE are able to shed light on the function of the studied earthen structures, developing hypothesis about possible identified natural and anthropogenic layers. To do so, principal component analysis (PCA) was employed to explore the geochemical datasets, reducing the number of variables. Finally, a methodological approach based on REE chemistry processes and their drivers (minor and major elements) was developed for the interpretation of possible natural or anthropogenic activities carried out in each studied earthen structure and also to identify the nature of the changing patterns. To conclude, the obtained soil data were cross-referenced with the scarce archaeological record composed by sherds, lithic materials and palaeo-biological discovered during fieldworks.

1.2 Previous studies and developed hypotheses

In the Brazilian territory of Acre, where most of the earth deposits are located within structures delimited by ditches, the soils are typical of environments with high rainfall and climatic conditions of tropical and subtropical areas. They are generally very deep and have been identified as "argisols, cambisols, luvisols, gleysols, latosols, vertisols, plinthosols" and "neosoils" (Bardales et al. 2010). The pH of the soils in the area is generally acid, rich in silicon, aluminium and iron oxides (Wadt 2002). A preliminary study in the Acre territory highlighted that the deposits of the earthen structures were located in the most ancient areas, where developed soils and degraded latosols and argisols are found (Carmo 2012). The morphological description of the soils in the Fazenda Atlântica and Cícero

Cara de Pau deposits permitted palaeosol identification with anomalous organic carbon levels, changes in the texture of the natural characteristics and the presence of archaeological materials in the surface and subsurface horizons (Carmo 2012). The soils of the Severino Calazans and Jacó Sá geoglyphs were extremely low in phosphorus. Samples collected in a dark brown soil layer presented slightly higher concentration of phosphorus, 18 mg/kg, compared to other samples collected in reddish layers. Carmo (2012) concluded in her study that the occupation and use of structures had not been of sufficient duration to produce high amount of phosphorus in the soil in these environmental conditions. These environments are characterised by rapid nutrient cycles in plants, poor weather conditions and soil leaching. Alternatively, the nature of their use has been unable to cause significant accumulation and subsequent decomposition of the organic materials.

During the last decades, archaeo-botanical studies in the Acre region have shed new light on the chrono-cultural context of the earthen structures. Studies carried out by Ranzi and Aguiar (2004) imply the possibility that these were built before the formation of the forest and that in the past Amazon consisted of savannah. Carmo (2012) found phytoliths in ceramic fragments, supporting the hypothesis that the ditches were constructed in a palaeoenvironment of grass and non-forest vegetation, very different from the current scenario. The analysed material demonstrated low levels of "biogenic silica", as shown by the phytolith morphotype identified (bastonete). These morphotypes are taxonomically related to the Poaceae family, which are phytolith-producing grasses of wide geographical distribution. These data may support the hypothesis that this Amazon region was previously dominated by a relatively open landscape such as pampa or savannah, with herbaceous plants, especially grasses. Some authors (Lui and Molina 2009) affirm that the region had a "domestication of vegetation", causing significant changes in the species distribution. The important changes in the ecology of the landscape included economic reorientations that were focused on the exploitation of specific plants and animals, including palms, fruit trees, edible roots and aquatic fauna. In addition, this domestication also reveals a heterogeneity associated with use of plants (edible, medicinal, ritual and for manufacture), found mainly along the main rivers of the region and on the margins of their floodplains. Other evidence for this diverse exploitation is found in the ethnographic writings of Cristóbal Acuña (1641), describing a very varied fauna and flora, emphasizing a great variety of animals and alimentary plants (bananas, guavas, pineapple, maize, cocoa, Brazilian chestnuts), roots of much sustenance such as yucca, sweet potato, palms of various genera, coconuts, dates as well as medicinal plants. All this suggests that the prehistoric native exercised a powerful and continuous influence, from the beginning of the Holocene, right through to the present day. This conclusion supports the hypothesis that part of what today we see as a "primary" forest, was actually an anthropogenic landscape, the result of conscious or unconscious human activity management

(human manipulation of organic and non-organic components of the environment) for thousands of years.

Supporting this hypothesis, Watling *et al.* (2018) in their recent study suggest that ancestors of the Geoglyphs builders were responsible for an intensification of landscape management around 4000 cal BP and a new type of inceptive niche construction in the region. They proposed that, as a result of the Geoglyph construction practices, a landscape with resources such as palms was created, and consequently a greater resource concentration in these areas commenced with a combination of crop cultivation and forest management. This hypothesis seems to be supported by Iriarte *et al.* (2020) who carried out the LIDAR survey observing distinctive architectural features. Their results suggest the possibility that after the Geoglyph culture the Amazonian Acre region was not abandoned, but a new village network system flourished. Sunaluoma *et al.* (2021), employing remotely sensed imagery and aerial vehicle surveys, obtained data suggesting that the roads connecting particular sites were articulate across various sites, highlighting that in Acre terrestrial movement responded to the archaeological evidence of villages interconnected by road networks. Souza (2022) studying the Acre geoglyph site of Tequinho suggests that this was a cultural and religious centre, its roads and paths being central to ritualistic ceremonies as well as landscape markers and boundaries.

However, against this cultural evolution interpretations, Pärssinen *et al.* (2020) recently provided new evidence of anthropogenic ash and charcoal accumulation in the Acre area dating back to *c.* 10 000 cal BP and carbon isotope ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) values suggested no important changes in climate and vegetation during Holocene. While Della Libera *et al.* (2022) also employing $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ record indicates an overall tendency towards a more humid tropical forest only during the last millennia. Nacimiento *et al.* (2022) collected palaeoecological records from lake sediments containing charcoal and from pollen analyses to understand how human land-use affected vegetation during the early to mid-Holocene in the Western Amazon. The authors observed that significant vegetation changes were only found centuries to millennia after the human presence, suggesting that the earliest occupants of Amazonia exerted no more than a gradual change on the forest. The early human occupations across Amazonia occurred mostly in areas bordering savannahs, where fires were a part of the natural vegetation dynamics. In these regions natural fires were common and could not be distinguished from anthropogenic fires based solely on charcoal counts.

Then, there are others who support a symbiosis between humans and environment. Ponte and Szlafsztein (2022), investigating the dynamics and periodisation of special social events, assumed that over time these human groups in Western Amazonia, including the Acre region, become familiar with the natural characteristics of the region to better understand the dynamics of its ecosystems,

consequently selecting plant species and ecosystems with greater utilitarian potential for their livelihood. Analyses of the dynamics of socio-spatial events demonstrate that humans have always established relationships with nature through their organisational and productive capacities, the latter conditioned by the available technology; and as humanity interacted with Amazonian natural environment their knowledge increased, enhancing conditions that facilitated socio-productive stabilisation. Maezumi *et al.* (2022) suggests that polyculture agroforestry and cultural burning persisted within this system during the Holocene. Likewise, Silva (2019) investigated by geomorphological techniques the construction techniques of these monuments showing that the base was made by mound, where material with clay and iron nodules were employed, probably to reinforce the structure, opposite the upper layers were made on coarser material (silt and sand). It is therefore apparent that the evidence presented by previous studies show diverse hypotheses which are in some ways contradictory regarding the development and function of the earthen structures. This inconclusive situation demonstrates the necessity for more archaeological data and the application of additional methods.

2. Materials and Methods

Soil samples were collected from the Geoglyphs of Antonio y Felipe (AyF) and of Pedro y Nelida (PyN), as aforementioned, located in the RESEX area (Fig. 1). The earthen structures were discovered by Agustín Diez-Castillo and collaborators during the Hispanic-Brazilian research collaboration that have been developed since 2017 (Diez Castillo *et al.* 2017; Rampanelli *et al.* 2017). Both earthen structures have been selected for this study because their formal features are characteristic of the area, and due to their optimal state of conservation and to logistical factors, such as the facility for obtaining permits, being within a federal reserve. AyF and PyN are located under the forest and are protected under the jurisdiction of RESEX. This is an area of high ecological value owned by the Brazilian state and in which traditional uses are allowed to both indigenous communities and traditional settlers (aka *serengeiros*) allowing the establishment of a long-term archaeological intervention strategy not conditioned by landowners roles. The first survey carried out showed that the material in these Geoglyphs is very limited (Rampanelli *et al.* 2017), although some interesting ceramic assemblages were recovered, as well as lithic materials and palaeo-biological remains during fieldwork (August 2022).

2.1 Sampling

Sampling data are reported in the Table 1.

Forty-five samples of sediment were collected from the geoglyphs of Antonio y Felipe (AyF) and of Pedro y Nelida (PyN). Concerning AyF, ten samples come from a cross-section in the bottom of the ditch (AyF2.01-10), characterised by a reddish and silty-sandy soils, and eight from a cross-section from an excavation in inner area (AyF3.01-08), characterised by a reddish and silty-sandy soils with laterites. Regarding PyN, the samples come from an excavation area in the upper inner area of the Geoglyph: seventeen from one of the main cross-sections (PyN2.01-17), characterised by a reddish and silty-sandy sediments with presence of ceramic shreds and carbons, and ten from a survey pit in the centre of the same area (PyN1.01-10), in which the sediment are clayey-sandy with presence of laterites and carbons.

2.2 Multielement analysis

Samples were air-dried, sieved to 2 mm, grounded and homogenised by an agate mortar.

Portable X-ray fluorescence (pXRF) analysis was performed with a S1 Titan portable energy dispersive pXRF spectrometer by Bruker equipped with an Rh X-ray tube and X-Flash® SDD detector. Geochem-trace calibration was used to obtain of Al, Si, K, Ca, Ti, Fe, Rb and Zr concentrations.

Trace elements analyses were performed using a NexION 2000 inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) by Perkin Elmer. Samples were digested by *aqua regia*, adding 1.35 mL of HCl and 0.45 mL of HNO₃ to 0.15 g of powdered sample in a glass tube, subsequently heated in a boiling water bath for about 40 min. Concentrations Li, Be, V, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, Sr, Mo, Cd, Ba, Tl, Pb, Bi, U, REE (La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, and Lu), Sc and Y were determined in the solution. Details on the analytical method can be found in Gallelo *et al.* (2022).

NIM-GBW07408 Soil certified reference material was analysed by both pXRF and ICP-MS to test the accuracy and precision of the analyses.

2.3 Data analysis

Data analysis was carried out by R (version: 4.4.1; R Core Team, 2024) and the following R packages were employed: factoextra (version: 1.0.7; Kassambara and Mundt, 2020), corrplot (version: 0.92; Wei and Simko, 2021), ggplot2 (version: 3.5.1; Wickham, 2016).

Data were explored by principal component analysis (PCA) which was carried out using all the samples as observations and all the elemental concentrations as variables. Variables were z-scored prior to the analysis.

2.4 Rare earth elements (REE) parameters

Several ratios are calculated for Ce and Eu anomalies, resulting from differential reactions associated with reduction-oxidation (Ce^{3+} or $^{4+}$ and Eu^{2+} or $^{3+}$) using formulae from Gallelo *et al.* (2021), detailed below. Anomalies are considered positive or negative depending on whether the values are above or below 1, respectively. Finally, fractionations (Gallelo *et al.* 2019) of light REE (**LREE**: La to Nd), medium REE (**MREE**: Sm to Ho) and heavy REE (**HREE**: Er to Lu) can be evaluated.

In order to calculate these ratios, normalized concentrations need to be use. These concentrations are written as “ X_n ” in the formulae, corresponding to the normalised concentration of an element X by Post Archean Australian Shale (PAAS) concentrations reported by Taylor and McLennan (1985) as follows.

$$[X_n] = \frac{[X]_{raw}}{PAAS_X}$$

Where $[X]_{raw}$ corresponds to the concentration of the element X after ICP-MS analysis and $PAAS_X$ correspond to the PAAS value of the element X.

Those normalised concentrations are then used to calculate anomalies and fractionation with the formulae as follow.

Anomalies from Gallelo *et al.* (2021):

$$\frac{Ce_n}{Ce^*} \quad \frac{Eu_n}{Eu^*}$$

$$Ce^* = \frac{La_n}{2} + \frac{Pr_n}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad Eu^* = \frac{Sm_n}{2} + \frac{Gd_n}{2}$$

Fractionations:

$$\frac{LREE}{HREE} = \frac{La_n}{Yb_n} ; \quad \frac{LREE}{MREE} = \frac{La_n}{Sm_n} ; \quad \frac{MREE}{HREE} = \frac{Sm_n}{Yb_n}$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Data exploration

Major, minor and trace elements concentrations, and REE, including Sc and Y, REE ratios and Ce, Eu anomalies parameters are in the supplementary materials (Annex 1, Tables A1.1 and A1.2). Principal component analysis was carried out to explore chemical data (Fig. 2).

As can be observed in the scores plot (Fig.2), samples from AyF and from PyN can be distinguished: most of the samples from PyN have higher scores in PC1 positive direction and lower ones in PC2 negative direction than those from AyF (except for some samples from PyN2). It is worth noting that, considering the two Geoglyphs, the samples collected from different cross-sections fall in different areas of the diagram. Indeed, samples from AyF2 (bottom of the ditch) have higher PC1 in negative direction and PC2 in positive direction than those from AyF3 (inner area), and samples from PyN2 (upper inner area) has higher PC2 scores and in most of the cases higher PC1 scores than PyN1 (upper inner area – survey pit).

Loadings plots for PC1 (Fig.2b) and for PC2 (Fig.2c) indicate the main features of the different classes of samples. Samples from PyN show higher levels of Al, Ti, Zr and Mo than AyF, while AyF ones show higher concentrations of K, Rb, Be, Co, Ni, Zn, Cd and Ba. For the other elements, the dissimilarities are fuzzier and involve inner differences between the cross-sections of the two geoglyphs. Concerning major elements levels, we can observe that cross-section PyN2 has higher Si levels than the others and low Ca ones, which is in most of the cases below the limit of detection. On the other hand, PyN1 has the highest Fe concentrations. As regards trace elements, PyN1 has the highest concentrations for V, Cr and Bi, and the lowest for Mn, while PyN2 has low amounts of Pb. Total REE levels are lower in AyF2 and PyN2 than in the other column of their respective Geoglyph, though for PyN differences are more blurred. Loadings for PC2 suggest that scores in this dimension are influenced also by REE fractionation. First, PyN is characterised by strong positive Ce anomalies, especially for low strata of PyN2 (PyN2.02-07), compared to AyF. Light REE are enriched over HREE, but this enrichment is less intense in AyF3, while MREE enrichment over HREE is more intense in PyN than in AyF. On the other hand, LREE are not enriched compared to MREE in all the columns and Eu anomalies are not present.

Correlations among elemental concentrations and REE parameters in the four cross-sections are shown in Fig.3. Drivers for REE levels seems to variate slightly from a Geoglyph to the others, and between columns of the same Geoglyph. Total amount of REE (TREE) is positively correlated with Fe in all the columns and with Sr in AyF2-3 and in PyN1. For PyN2 and AyF2, it shows a moderate

positive correlation with K. In PyN2, levels of REE seem to be driven also by Al in the positive direction, and by Si, Ca, Ti and Mn in the negative one. Ce anomalies have negative correlations with Fe for both PyN1 and PyN2, while it is moderately positively correlated with Mn for PyN2 and negatively for PyN1. In PyN2, it shows strong positively correlations also with Si and Ti, while moderate negative correlation can be observed with Al. No significant correlations have been found between the selected elements and the parameters for LREE enrichment in PyN1. On the other hand, La_n/Yb_n and La_n/Sm_n are correlated in a positive direction with Mn in AyF2, and the latter in the negative one with Fe. For AyF3, we can observe positive correlations between La_n/Yb_n and Sr, and between La_n/Sm_n and Ca. In PyN2, strong positive correlations are present between La_n/Sm_n and Si, Ti, and strong negative one with Fe, while moderate correlations seems to be present with Al and K(negative), and with Mn (positive). Significant correlations for Sm_n/Yb_n were found only for AyF3 and PyF2. In particular, MREE enrichment over HREE is driven by Sr for AyF3, and it shows strong positive correlations with Fe and strong negative ones with Si in PyN2. Moderate positive correlations are present between Sm_n/Yb_n , and Al and K, and moderate negative ones between the above-quoted ratio and Ca, Ti and Mn.

Comparing the columns from the geoglyphs permits to better highlight some patterns. As can be observed in the boxplot graphs (Fig. 4), survey pit sediments (PyN1), which allegedly contains natural strata, show the highest enrichment of Al and Fe, and the lowest concentrations for Mn, while PyN1, from which area remains of human activities were found, have the lower levels of Si and the lowest ones of K and Fe. PyN2 has also the levels with the highest positive anomalies for Ce and the highest positive enrichment of MREE over HREE.

3.2 REE chemical processes in AyF and PyN soils

These preliminary chemical data show that differences among Geoglyphs and related sections are probably based mainly on natural processes. However, some human induced chemical processes have taken action and have contributed to the strata formation.

The soils in the studied area are from reddish silty-sandy material and, as suggested by previous works, pH of the soils in the area is generally acid, and as confirmed by our study, it is rich in silicon, aluminium and iron oxides (Wadt 2002). The obtained data are also in accordance to those already observed in the soils of the Geoglyphs of Severino Calazans and Jacó Sá low, which are poor in phosphorus (Carmo 2012).

In general, as already observed in Brazilian mangrove soils, REE depletion and fractionation are driven by clay minerals (Andrade et al. 2022). In our studied sections, natural soil samples from

PyN1(survey pit) show higher concentrations of REE especially in the bottom of the pit compared to most of the samples from PyN2, where archaeological material were found. This may be because REE are retained onto the clay mineral phases (Gallelo et al. 2019), resulting in higher concentration of REE in the PyN1. Furthermore, both Geoglyphs AyF and PyN sections present positive Ce anomalies, typical of clay rich in Fe (Pattan et al 2005). However, the AyF2 and AyF3 present higher levels of Sr and Ca than PyN, being those elements representing carbonate phases (Gallelo et al. 2019) and higher concentrations of K maybe in this case related to the aluminosilicate, thus influencing the REE behavior as reflected in the minor values of Ce anomaly and Sm_n/Yb_n . Most of the samples present neutral Eu anomalies, possibly related to the dominance of silicates (Si and Al are the most abundant elements) in the studied soils fraction (Cuadro et al. 2023).

While AyF2, AyF3 and PyN1 chemical profiles probably are influenced by natural processes, PyN2, which is the only section related to archaeological remains, presents the highest Si concentrations.. Given that Si levels are not correlated to those of Al, this is maybe related to the presence phytoliths, as suggested by Carmo (2012) work that found them associated to ceramic fragments, and/or of authigenic amorphous silica and Si-rich clay minerals possibly originated from the precipitation of biogenic silica from vegetal remains (Karkanis 2010).

These data suggest that Si could be related to human activities and, consequently, the REE concentrations, fractionations and anomalies employed could mark the human contribution to the soil development and formation.

4. Conclusions

Rare earth elements soil analyses have been employed for the first time in Geoglyphs of Antonio y Felipe (AyF) and of Pedro y Nelida (PyN), located in the RESEX area. The obtained data show the potential of REE to identify anthropogenic deposits in a very complex environment and site with scarce archaeological record.

REE concentrations, fractionations and anomalies cross-referenced with major and minor elements and archaeological record, provided innovative proxies to determine past human activities in this geometrical earthwork located in the Acre State (Brazil) where those remains are significantly found. The capability of REE as a key tool to understand the history of these archaeological remains need to be explored. The obtained results have demonstrated the important role of REE to clarify a pivotal issue such as the understanding of the human contribution to the development of archaeological deposits in the studied area. However, this approach needs to be optimised to reach a better comprehension of the anthropogenic contribution to the development of the strata in the earthen structures employing REE chemistry and identifying its drivers to provide a new tool to understand

contexts characterised by scarce amount of remains, where the traditional geochemical and archaeological methods have not proven to be sufficiently reliable.

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Table and Figures Captions

Table 1. Sampling data.

Fig. 1. Area of study and sampling section location for the Geoglyphs AyF and PyN.

Fig. 2. Samples/scores plot (a) of PCA and variables/loadings plots for PC1 (b) and PC2 (c).

Fig. 3. Pearson correlation coefficients (r) for REE parameters and elemental concentrations. Non-significant coefficients ($p > 0.05$) are barred.

Fig. 4. Distributions of elemental concentrations and REE parameters in the four columns (outliers were not considered).

Table 1. Collected samples and provenance.

Sample	Geoglyph	Location	Height	Sample	Geoglyph	Location	Height
AyF2.01	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	297.40	PyN1.06	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	98.00
AyF2.02	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	297.50	PyN1.07	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	98.10
AyF2.03	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	297.60	PyN1.08	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	98.20
AyF2.04	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	297.70	PyN1.09	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	98.30
AyF2.05	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	297.80	PyN1.10	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	98.40
AyF2.06	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	297.90	PyN2.17	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.40
AyF2.07	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	298.00	PyN2.16	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.45
AyF2.08	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	298.10	PyN2.15	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.50
AyF2.09	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	298.20	PyN2.14	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.55
AyF2.10	Antonio y Felipe	Bottom of the ditch	298.30	PyN2.13	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.60
AyF3.01	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	298.30	PyN2.12	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.65
AyF3.02	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	298.40	PyN2.11	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.70
AyF3.03	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	298.50	PyN2.10	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.75
AyF3.04	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	298.60	PyN2.09	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.80
AyF3.05	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	298.70	PyN2.08	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.85
AyF3.06	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	298.80	PyN2.07	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.90
AyF3.07	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	298.90	PyN2.06	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	98.95
AyF3.08	Antonio y Felipe	Inner area	299.00	PyN2.05	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	99.00
PyN1.01	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	97.20	PyN2.04	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	99.05
PyN1.02	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	97.50	PyN2.03	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	99.10
PyN1.03	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	97.60	PyN2.02	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	99.15
PyN1.04	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	97.70	PyN2.01	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area	99.20
PyN1.05	Pedro y Nelida	Upper inner area (survey pit)	97.90				

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 4

ANNEX

Table A1.1. Concentrations of major element and trace elements expressed as percentage (from Al to Fe) or mg/kg (from Rb to U)

Samples	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti	Fe	Rb	Zr	Li	Be	V	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Zn	Sr	Mo	Cd	Ba	Tl	Pb	Bi	U
AyF2.01	11.72	21.88	1.15	0.02	0.61	5.03	52	307	1.39	0.613	52.4	21.3	368	4.31	8.87	40.2	7.22	0.403	0.029	31.0	0.075	15.8	0.110	5.67
AyF2.02	11.24	22.79	1.08	0.02	0.59	4.60	51	317	1.05	0.574	45.2	14.6	229	3.43	6.76	6.00	5.85	0.301	0.018	17.7	0.055	12.0	0.097	4.68
AyF2.03	11.26	22.63	1.06	0.01	0.60	4.64	49	318	1.05	0.533	49.2	23.1	258	3.44	6.70	4.52	5.81	0.347	0.022	23.0	0.060	13.1	0.110	4.75
AyF2.04	8.74	20.73	0.94	<LD	0.57	4.56	47	328	0.984	0.392	42.8	17.4	266	3.36	6.09	90.7	5.83	0.407	0.017	19.5	0.058	11.0	0.081	4.47
AyF2.05	11.18	25.01	1.02	0.01	0.61	4.54	50	366	0.899	0.479	43.1	15.0	259	3.73	6.26	33.5	5.36	0.220	0.012	19.0	0.061	11.5	0.083	4.49
AyF2.06	9.42	21.53	0.97	0.01	0.61	4.32	55	353	0.952	0.539	48.9	16.5	336	4.38	7.03	83.2	5.98	0.265	0.021	22.4	0.071	11.8	0.097	4.95
AyF2.07	10.10	23.09	1.01	<LD	0.60	4.63	55	389	0.815	0.406	46.2	23.4	469	5.42	6.22	55.1	5.60	0.255	0.029	17.8	0.063	12.8	0.092	4.41
AyF2.08	13.62	27.62	1.09	0.02	0.62	4.33	51	384	0.920	0.409	43.0	12.5	613	5.36	6.63	43.4	6.15	0.433	0.030	23.4	0.085	13.7	0.089	4.26
AyF2.09	8.80	21.37	0.96	0.01	0.59	4.13	51	342	0.933	0.454	42.1	14.4	682	5.23	6.32	49.3	5.96	0.382	0.073	21.7	0.070	13.6	0.082	4.24
AyF2.10	10.15	24.75	1.00	0.01	0.61	4.06	49	344	1.02	0.396	43.4	13.2	772	5.17	6.68	37.4	6.49	0.509	0.038	25.4	0.076	14.1	0.079	4.47
Mean	10.6	23	1.03	0.014	0.601	4.5	51	345	51	0.48	46	17	425	4.4	6.8	44	6.0	0.35	0.029	22	0.067	12.9	0.092	4.6
s	1.5	2	0.07	0.002	0.015	0.3	2	28	2	0.08	3	4	198	0.9	0.8	28	0.5	0.09	0.017	4	0.010	1.4	0.011	0.4
AyF3.01	14.63	22.02	1.30	0.02	0.61	5.64	59	303	1.91	0.655	51.8	17.8	183	3.73	8.49	42.4	7.98	0.353	0.020	36.8	0.082	13.6	0.106	6.03
AyF3.02	15.10	23.45	1.25	0.01	0.60	5.60	66	310	1.79	0.607	56.9	21.2	184	3.64	8.11	47.7	8.02	0.606	0.031	35.8	0.086	13.7	0.160	5.95
AyF3.03	12.30	20.12	1.21	0.01	0.59	5.56	63	363	1.99	0.616	53.4	17.1	183	3.61	8.31	50.9	8.48	0.305	0.025	36.2	0.080	13.6	0.126	5.81
AyF3.04	13.78	22.38	1.14	0.02	0.59	5.70	65	357	2.07	0.569	57.0	28.3	181	3.52	8.20	40.9	7.71	0.180	0.021	34.0	0.082	13.8	0.110	6.10
AyF3.05	13.66	21.76	1.15	0.01	0.60	6.02	64	357	2.61	0.605	62.2	28.1	241	3.96	8.87	28.8	10.2	0.414	0.030	49.6	0.110	16.8	0.125	6.51
AyF3.06	10.20	18.69	1.04	0.01	0.56	5.93	63	357	1.97	0.463	56.9	33.3	193	3.19	7.29	33.5	8.11	0.239	0.039	40.4	0.083	13.9	0.122	5.48
AyF3.07	10.30	19.28	1.00	0.01	0.57	5.71	64	320	2.16	0.545	60.3	31.4	222	3.47	7.87	38.6	9.38	0.441	0.034	44.6	0.102	15.0	0.134	5.76
AyF3.08	12.15	23.43	1.10	0.01	0.61	5.00	58	270	1.54	0.443	48.4	18.4	219	3.54	6.80	46.5	7.14	0.270	0.032	33.9	0.079	12.1	0.102	5.30
Mean	12.8	21.4	1.15	0.015	0.590	5.6	63	330	2.0	0.56	56	24	201	3.6	8.0	41	8.4	0.35	0.029	39	0.088	14.1	0.123	5.9
s	1.9	1.8	0.10	0.003	0.018	0.3	3	34	0.3	0.08	4	7	23	0.2	0.7	7	1.0	0.13	0.007	6	0.012	1.4	0.018	0.4
PyN1.01	15.93	20.71	0.74	0.01	0.71	8.66	43	528	3.56	0.272	144	39.6	160	1.76	5.53	13.7	7.24	0.453	<LD	12.9	0.098	15.6	0.227	5.15
PyN1.02	14.81	18.68	0.76	0.01	0.73	9.44	47	454	3.15	0.242	167	66.9	162	1.83	5.04	18.0	8.18	0.500	0.022	17.1	0.099	18.1	0.214	6.06
PyN1.03	16.50	19.44	0.75	0.01	0.71	12.20	43	436	3.32	0.312	272	116.9	152	1.98	5.95	26.7	10.8	1.617	0.025	18.8	0.108	25.2	0.393	8.09
PyN1.04	15.48	20.51	0.82	<LD	0.77	8.30	45	498	2.49	0.222	160	65.9	151	1.73	4.97	18.9	7.49	1.008	0.018	14.2	0.091	16.4	0.249	5.59
PyN1.05	19.43	26.38	0.84	0.01	0.74	6.81	41	557	2.39	0.199	143	63.9	156	1.63	4.50	18.9	7.02	0.626	0.024	14.0	0.087	14.8	0.212	4.74
PyN1.06	14.89	21.90	0.80	<LD	0.81	7.04	43	539	2.41	0.197	152	65.8	167	1.72	4.94	20.5	7.16	1.103	0.014	16.3	0.090	14.6	0.248	5.01
PyN1.07	15.11	21.92	0.80	<LD	0.75	7.15	43	498	2.09	0.185	122	56.6	150	1.55	4.06	5.09	6.15	0.843	0.012	15.8	0.081	12.8	0.198	4.24
PyN1.08	15.30	22.49	0.79	<LD	0.78	7.31	44	562	2.07	0.233	170	72.3	131	1.47	4.28	15.6	7.91	0.732	0.017	19.7	0.078	16.0	0.214	4.96
PyN1.09	18.79	27.21	0.82	0.04	0.74	8.32	40	512	1.74	0.230	161	82.9	130	1.24	3.52	2.95	7.33	0.889	0.013	17.2	0.073	15.1	0.213	4.41
PyN1.10	12.75	21.83	0.74	0.02	0.77	4.77	38	575	1.81	0.111	59.9	20.0	142	1.52	3.72	10.7	4.68	0.661	<LD	15.5	0.069	8.24	0.136	3.67
Mean	16	22	0.78	0.017	0.75	8	43	516	2.5	0.22	155	65	150	1.6	4.6	15	7.4	0.8	0.018	16	0.087	16	0.23	5.2
s	2	3	0.04	0.011	0.03	2	3	46	0.6	0.05	52	25	13	0.2	0.8	7	1.6	0.3	0.005	2	0.012	4	0.07	1.2
PyN2.01	10.20	38.80	0.54	0.15	0.76	3.19	17	678	0.449	0.052	47.4	25.9	513	1.67	2.80	<LD	7.37	0.740	0.029	23.0	0.032	8.04	0.078	1.57
PyN2.02	11.44	37.42	0.62	0.05	0.90	2.95	22	828	0.428	0.097	44.8	19.8	493	1.83	2.64	<LD	5.61	0.771	0.014	16.2	0.032	8.27	0.083	1.90
PyN2.03	14.48	41.35	0.69	0.04	0.97	2.94	20	804	0.526	0.065	44.7	18.6	537	2.12	2.89	<LD	5.53	0.878	0.016	18.1	0.036	8.97	0.104	2.28
PyN2.04	11.10	36.46	0.63	0.02	0.98	2.79	22	933	0.596	0.071	44.1	15.7	517	2.35	3.19	<LD	4.94	0.644	0.014	16.6	0.044	9.55	0.084	2.65
PyN2.05	13.28	36.90	0.67	0.01	0.95	3.25	23	858	0.613	0.083	46.9	19.5	413	2.06	2.81	<LD	4.87	0.711	0.020	15.3	0.045	9.73	0.095	2.58
PyN2.06	10.97	34.99	0.59	<LD	0.88	3.08	25	890	0.817	0.103	54.2	18.4	358	2.35	3.42	<LD	4.98	0.924	0.015	13.6	0.053	9.67	0.124	3.16
PyN2.07	11.34	30.59	0.69	<LD	0.96	3.49	27	856	0.819	0.085	58.4	28.6	253	1.90	2.91	<LD	4.66	0.823	0.013	13.2	0.049	10.3	0.124	3.09
PyN2.08	12.14	27.12	0.72	<LD	0.94	3.88	29	734	1.25	0.110	58.2	21.9	226	1.91	3.71	3.88	4.95	0.923	0.014	16.6	0.064	9.33	0.134	3.37
PyN2.09	14.82	33.32	0.64	<LD	0.83	4.06	32	763	1.49	0.154	61.2	23.1	226	1.99	3.87	<LD	5.14	0.609	0.017	20.8	0.075	10.2	0.125	4.05
PyN2.10	12.92	28.53	0.67	<LD	0.78	4.11	33	646	1.66	0.172	60.9	21.6	278	2.07	4.22	28.2	5.19	0.530	0.020	23.3	0.078	11.2	0.124	4.34
PyN2.11	14.74	28.69	0.70	<LD	0.77	4.16	36	567	1.81	0.164	57.5	16.6	475	2.10	4.28	<LD	5.00	0.524	0.019	23.6	0.283	11.7	0.148	4.40
PyN2.12	14.97	32.09	0.67	<LD	0.73	4.05	33	584	1.74	0.173	67.4	19.9	416	2.10	4.10	12.6	5.48	0.984	0.029	22.0	0.118	11.3	0.161	4.19
PyN2.13	15.28	27.56	0.74	<LD	0.80	3.83	33	604	1.21	0.079	51.2	16.1	222	1.64	3.24	11.9	4.31	0.430	0.012	14.1	0.081	7.95	0.116	3.16
PyN2.14	12.00	25.75	0.69	0.01	0.75	3.94	34	610	1.36	0.128	58.0	17.2	203	1.80	3.76	<LD	4.93	0.707	0.013	18.2	0.079	8.49	0.139	3.57
PyN2.15	15.01	25.05	0.79	<LD	0.81	4.44	36	633	1.59	0.144	66.2	23.1	178	1.66	3.76	<LD	5.29	0.561	0.011	17.5	0.079	9.40	0.143	3.76
PyN2.16	15.91	26.74	0.70	<LD	0.76	4.72	38	586	1.63	0.146	82.6	27.1	189	1.74	4.06	<LD	5.67	0.768	0.018	19.0	0.077	10.6	0.174	4.24
PyN2.17	14.09	29.06	0.69	<LD	0.76	4.65	37	622	1.71	0.158	103	29.9	179	1.72	3.99	<LD	5.68	0.973	0.011	17.4	0.083	10.3	0.187	4.00
Mean	13.2	32	0.67	0.05	0.84	3.7	29	717	1.2	0.12	59	21	334	1.9	3.5	14	5.3	0.74	0.017	18	0.08	9.7	0.13	3.3
s	1.8	5	0.06	0.05	0.09	0.6	7	123																

Table A1.2. Concentrations of REE, expressed as mg/kg, and REE parameters.

Sample	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Sc	Y	TREE	Ce _n /Ce*	Eu _n /Eu*	La _n /Yb _n	La _n /Sm _n	Sm _n /Yb _n
AyF2.01	21.2	59.4	5.20	20.7	4.00	0.833	3.29	0.417	2.26	0.373	0.951	0.121	0.720	0.097	6.88	9.09	120	1.30	1.07	2.17	0.78	2.78
AyF2.02	16.6	49.5	4.07	16.3	3.12	0.646	2.63	0.335	1.81	0.306	0.788	0.096	0.578	0.080	5.81	7.46	97	1.38	1.05	2.12	0.79	2.69
AyF2.03	15.9	49.0	3.91	15.4	2.97	0.635	2.56	0.325	1.78	0.292	0.734	0.096	0.566	0.078	5.98	7.13	94	1.43	1.07	2.07	0.79	2.63
AyF2.04	14.8	46.2	3.62	14.1	2.81	0.563	2.23	0.294	1.53	0.255	0.629	0.079	0.493	0.065	5.22	6.01	88	1.45	1.05	2.21	0.77	2.85
AyF2.05	13.3	42.8	3.26	12.7	2.52	0.530	2.19	0.277	1.53	0.251	0.634	0.085	0.524	0.070	5.18	6.26	81	1.49	1.05	1.87	0.78	2.40
AyF2.06	14.2	40.3	3.38	13.2	2.63	0.571	2.26	0.287	1.58	0.267	0.659	0.086	0.537	0.071	5.37	6.62	80	1.34	1.09	1.94	0.79	2.45
AyF2.07	12.3	35.6	2.98	11.6	2.27	0.467	1.97	0.250	1.37	0.240	0.603	0.080	0.463	0.060	5.06	5.81	70	1.35	1.03	1.96	0.80	2.44
AyF2.08	14.8	40.0	3.46	13.5	2.55	0.556	2.16	0.277	1.52	0.250	0.647	0.083	0.477	0.066	4.75	6.21	80	1.29	1.11	2.28	0.85	2.68
AyF2.09	14.1	41.7	3.33	13.0	2.39	0.494	2.06	0.255	1.37	0.230	0.571	0.071	0.449	0.059	4.92	5.65	80	1.40	1.04	2.31	0.87	2.66
AyF2.10	14.3	45.4	3.30	12.5	2.40	0.487	1.92	0.253	1.28	0.214	0.530	0.069	0.437	0.056	5.20	5.16	83	1.52	1.06	2.40	0.87	2.75
Mean	15	45	3.7	14	2.8	0.58	2.3	0.30	1.6	0.27	0.67	0.087	0.52	0.070	5.4	6.5	87	1.39	1.06	2.13	0.81	2.63
s	2	7	0.6	3	0.5	0.11	0.4	0.05	0.3	0.05	0.12	0.015	0.08	0.012	0.6	1.1	14	0.08	0.02	0.17	0.04	0.15
AyF3.01	20.5	52.0	5.23	20.9	4.14	0.874	3.62	0.467	2.48	0.442	1.12	0.146	0.854	0.119	7.19	10.8	113	1.15	1.05	1.77	0.73	2.42
AyF3.02	19.7	50.6	5.10	20.2	4.10	0.869	3.52	0.443	2.45	0.424	1.08	0.139	0.837	0.116	7.10	10.6	110	1.16	1.07	1.73	0.71	2.45
AyF3.03	20.6	51.5	5.29	21.4	4.17	0.897	3.66	0.474	2.56	0.436	1.10	0.143	0.842	0.116	7.06	10.8	113	1.14	1.07	1.80	0.73	2.48
AyF3.04	19.9	49.7	5.06	20.7	4.06	0.869	3.58	0.457	2.49	0.433	1.09	0.143	0.870	0.122	7.53	10.8	109	1.14	1.06	1.69	0.72	2.34
AyF3.05	22.8	58.6	5.95	23.8	4.69	1.026	4.00	0.510	2.75	0.476	1.19	0.155	0.921	0.129	8.00	11.2	127	1.16	1.10	1.82	0.72	2.55
AyF3.06	17.9	53.4	4.62	18.8	3.81	0.793	3.28	0.417	2.24	0.382	0.994	0.127	0.782	0.107	7.19	9.03	108	1.35	1.05	1.69	0.69	2.43
AyF3.07	18.8	57.9	4.93	19.8	3.89	0.838	3.37	0.446	2.27	0.381	0.956	0.129	0.770	0.107	7.58	8.84	115	1.38	1.08	1.80	0.71	2.53
AyF3.08	15.3	52.9	3.96	16.1	3.30	0.697	2.81	0.371	2.01	0.339	0.839	0.113	0.688	0.098	6.55	8.10	100	1.56	1.07	1.64	0.68	2.40
Mean	19	53	5.0	20	4.0	0.86	3.5	0.45	2.4	0.41	1.05	0.14	0.82	0.114	7.3	10.0	112	1.25	1.07	1.74	0.71	2.45
s	2	3	0.6	2	0.4	0.09	0.3	0.04	0.2	0.04	0.11	0.01	0.07	0.010	0.4	1.2	8	0.16	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.07
PyN1.01	12.6	66.3	3.54	14.3	2.66	0.484	1.76	0.195	1.00	0.166	0.437	0.061	0.358	0.052	11.1	3.70	104	2.27	1.04	2.59	0.70	3.72
PyN1.02	12.4	62.0	3.65	14.7	2.77	0.506	1.84	0.202	1.05	0.165	0.443	0.061	0.386	0.053	10.8	3.63	100	2.11	1.04	2.36	0.66	3.59
PyN1.03	13.9	72.1	4.04	16.6	3.10	0.595	1.99	0.225	1.14	0.184	0.487	0.066	0.436	0.057	13.8	4.08	115	2.20	1.11	2.35	0.66	3.55
PyN1.04	11.5	61.9	3.46	14.5	2.75	0.520	1.83	0.203	1.04	0.165	0.434	0.061	0.369	0.055	10.1	3.38	99	2.24	1.07	2.30	0.62	3.73
PyN1.05	10.1	56.3	3.18	13.2	2.54	0.461	1.66	0.176	0.954	0.148	0.378	0.052	0.346	0.051	9.23	2.96	90	2.26	1.04	2.16	0.59	3.68
PyN1.06	9.65	60.7	3.10	12.8	2.67	0.491	1.66	0.191	0.961	0.151	0.402	0.055	0.375	0.051	9.55	2.98	93	2.52	1.08	1.90	0.53	3.57
PyN1.07	8.01	56.4	2.65	11.1	2.25	0.421	1.45	0.159	0.861	0.134	0.343	0.049	0.307	0.042	8.50	2.51	84	2.77	1.08	1.92	0.53	3.65
PyN1.08	8.42	59.0	2.76	11.5	2.40	0.431	1.55	0.176	0.895	0.141	0.369	0.052	0.326	0.046	9.37	2.64	88	2.78	1.03	1.90	0.52	3.68
PyN1.09	7.65	51.9	2.57	10.7	2.33	0.439	1.49	0.166	0.835	0.132	0.345	0.045	0.330	0.045	8.26	2.44	79	2.65	1.09	1.71	0.48	3.52
PyN1.10	7.03	50.4	2.28	9.60	1.98	0.374	1.29	0.147	0.731	0.114	0.298	0.041	0.283	0.037	7.04	2.20	75	2.86	1.08	1.83	0.52	3.50
Mean	10	60	3.1	12.9	2.5	0.47	1.7	0.18	0.95	0.15	0.39	0.054	0.35	0.049	9.8	3.1	93	2.47	1.06	2.10	0.58	3.62
s	2	6	0.6	2.2	0.3	0.06	0.2	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.06	0.008	0.04	0.006	1.9	0.6	12	0.28	0.03	0.29	0.07	0.08
PyN2.01	2.06	13.6	0.537	2.14	0.446	0.075	0.287	0.035	0.179	0.030	0.081	0.012	0.075	0.009	2.33	0.608	20	2.97	0.97	2.03	0.68	2.99
PyN2.02	1.88	16.2	0.439	1.70	0.350	0.072	0.265	0.031	0.171	0.029	0.074	0.010	0.077	0.011	2.45	0.530	21	4.11	1.10	1.79	0.79	2.26
PyN2.03	2.31	21.1	0.566	2.29	0.445	0.086	0.337	0.041	0.225	0.037	0.093	0.014	0.077	0.012	3.10	0.681	28	4.25	1.03	2.20	0.76	2.88
PyN2.04	3.03	30.4	0.789	3.11	0.639	0.118	0.446	0.054	0.274	0.045	0.112	0.018	0.107	0.013	3.75	0.864	39	4.51	1.03	2.08	0.70	2.98
PyN2.05	3.48	34.1	0.924	3.49	0.718	0.140	0.539	0.060	0.333	0.055	0.129	0.018	0.113	0.017	4.15	1.04	44	4.36	1.05	2.26	0.71	3.17
PyN2.06	5.29	43.5	1.47	5.76	1.14	0.211	0.829	0.093	0.483	0.074	0.190	0.026	0.175	0.023	5.17	1.55	59	3.57	1.01	2.23	0.68	3.26
PyN2.07	5.34	41.8	1.51	5.95	1.21	0.220	0.836	0.093	0.512	0.079	0.201	0.027	0.180	0.025	5.12	1.60	58	3.37	1.02	2.18	0.65	3.36
PyN2.08	7.54	50.9	2.14	8.59	1.69	0.335	1.17	0.136	0.706	0.117	0.299	0.039	0.251	0.037	6.15	2.33	74	2.90	1.11	2.21	0.66	3.37
PyN2.09	9.66	60.5	2.89	11.7	2.29	0.450	1.60	0.176	0.931	0.148	0.380	0.054	0.321	0.046	7.44	3.04	91	2.61	1.09	2.22	0.62	3.56
PyN2.10	11.6	68.5	3.65	15.2	3.02	0.574	1.99	0.224	1.18	0.181	0.463	0.062	0.406	0.055	8.16	3.75	107	2.40	1.09	2.10	0.56	3.72
PyN2.11	14.0	77.0	4.78	19.6	4.11	0.739	2.60	0.296	1.50	0.236	0.591	0.079	0.498	0.077	9.61	4.57	126	2.13	1.04	2.07	0.50	4.13
PyN2.12	12.7	67.6	4.21	17.8	3.54	0.643	2.29	0.252	1.31	0.202	0.553	0.068	0.455	0.061	8.22	4.06	112	2.09	1.04	2.06	0.53	3.89
PyN2.13	9.62	49.4	3.21	13.4	2.67	0.494	1.68	0.184	0.928	0.154	0.385	0.055	0.358	0.047	6.51	2.94	83	2.01	1.08	1.98	0.53	3.73
PyN2.14	9.60	49.0	3.17	13.5	2.66	0.513	1.69	0.177	0.928	0.147	0.385	0.051	0.327	0.048	7.14	2.87	82	2.01	1.12	2.16	0.53	4.06
PyN2.15	9.58	50.1	3.17	13.2	2.65	0.495	1.71	0.188	0.929	0.146	0.398	0.051	0.342	0.053	7.46	2.92	83	2.06	1.07	2.06	0.53	3.88
PyN2.16	9.99	58.0	3.44	14.5	2.94	0.558	1.92	0.220	1.08	0.171	0.451	0.060	0.412	0.053	8.14	3.17	94	2.23	1.09	1.79	0.50	3.57
PyN2.17	7.96	53.3	2.62	11.0	2.32	0.433	1.49	0.171	0.839	0.135	0.350	0.050	0.323	0.048	7.64	2.58	81	2.65	1.08	1.82	0.51	3.59
Mean	7	46	2.3	10	1.9	0.4	1.3	0.14	0.7	0.12	0.30	0.04	0.26	0.04	6.0	2.3	71	2.95	1.06	2.07	0.62	3.44
s	4	18	1.4	6	1.2	0.2	0.7	0.08	0.4	0.06	0.17	0.02	0.14	0.02	2.2	1.3	32	0.90	0.04	0.15	0.10	0.48

Note: TREE = REE sum (from La to Yb).